

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: LANG****FIRST NAME: LYNNE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied XUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx% - I used Grammarly Premium, but didn't see this %

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic essay (EUCLID 2024, 7-10)
2. Referencing the essay (EUCLID 2024, 10)
3. Style guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)
4. CMS crib sheet (EUCLID 2024, 43-57)
5. Sample corrections to papers (EUCLID 2024, 65-71)

BEGIN WITH A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

I hesitate to imagine the amount of writing required to complete the Doctor of Philosophy in Mediation and Conflict Resolution (DMCR). However, I understand that every long journey starts with the first step. For more than ten years, I have considered going back to school to pursue an advanced degree, and I found the EUCLID program to be the perfect fit for my goals. A few years ago, I applied for a Doctor of Public Health program, but only 100 students were selected from 1,000 applicants. When I discovered that I could start the EUCLID program at any time and study independently, I knew it was the right choice for me. This program aligns perfectly with my interest in community health and well-being, particularly within communities struggling with conflict.

The orientation and ACA-401D course packets provided by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (2024) remained unopened until I purchased a new computer for depositing all doctoral degree work over the next few years. After the new computer arrived, I downloaded the foundational documents for the coursework onto the new laptop. I pored over them carefully, knowing I must begin writing about learned lessons from the ACA-401D course pack. This response paper will include topics on

writing the essay, referencing the essay, style guide, CMS crib sheet, and sample corrections to papers.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY

Remembering the organization and flow of the essay is essential in forming a point of view on a topic. Highlighting and taking notes while reading will keep me on task with the progression of ideas and how to organize them. One important reason for me to earn a doctorate is to learn professional academic writing. As a creative writer, the section on essay writing is an essential reminder that academic writing is different. I am an excellent public speaker. However, my written ideas need fine-tuning by integrating creative and critical thinking (EUCLID 2024, 9). Researching opposing points of view can strengthen my point of view for readers. The pyramid (EUCLID 2024, 10) illustrates the structure I need as I read, research, outline, and write essays. Having a checklist to review before handing a paper in will be essential as I work on each assignment.

Giving myself plenty of time on a given assignment means no procrastinating! Scheduling time for schoolwork will prevent problems with time management. Moreover, after defining and analyzing the question, I will have ample time to draft the initial plan regarding my research topic for the assignments. These elements of the essay process will hopefully lead to a quality product by having time to thoughtfully produce an essay with an introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2024, 7-8).

3) REFERENCING THE ESSAY

Proper referencing is foundational in writing an essay so that readers can verify the source of information. I first learned about the Turabian (Chicago Rules) manual for writing when I enrolled in this course, so I will need to study the manual and master the Chicago Rules (Turabian). In previous coursework, I used MLA and APA and needed to check my citations. The best way to learn is by writing and challenging myself to properly cite sources using given examples and reading the reference manual provided. Having professors note necessary corrections is part of the learning journey. This particular assignment is a great way to get me thinking about the academic writing process and introduce myself to you.

4) STYLE GUIDE

The style guide states that I should use American English, and I am relieved, knowing that this international course could require a different language. Style guides serve to provide consistent expectations for both writers and readers. This is important for emphasizing the quality of content without questioning sources and giving a consistent voice to the overall style of a publication. Punctuation, grammar, sentence structure, and accepted terminology are examples of items prescribed in style guides. Successful writers will follow guidelines for many publications, as these expectations vary. Being familiar

with what is expected precedes any writing assignment and can save time editing and proofreading the piece.

As a creative writer, style guides have had more impact on my work since working on both of my master's degrees. In my undergraduate studies, one of the first purchases I made for writing was Strunk's 'The Elements of Style' (1972). It was sold in a rummage sale years later when I thought I was finished using it and imagined it would be updated if I needed a style guide again.

Learning to conform to a set of standards and using properly cited sources has been a good exercise in the discipline of writing. My earlier independent writing was submitted as articles or independent publications. Having friends with experience in technical writing, I know that the challenge of writing for a specific audience demands using a precise style guide. Although it will be a learning curve, I look forward to studying using the appropriate guide.

5) CMS CRIB SHEET

The title, *CMS CRIB SHEET* (EUCLID 2024, 44), refers to the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS 2003), which is also referenced as Turabian style (CMS 2003). I chuckled when I learned that a crib sheet is a "cheat sheet" (Merriam-Webster 2024), which can be grounds for failing an exam. I typically refer to a crib sheet as something placed in a baby's bed. However, in this instance, using a cheat sheet to help with Chicago style, page formatting, and end notes is encouraged and expected.

Proper usage of abbreviations and acronyms is outlined on page 44, and I learned that these elements of style should only be used when it is clear to the reader what they mean. Thus, both must be used with prudence.

Quotations, italics, and quotation marks were familiar to me from previous writings, but I could not find the exact information on numbers such as: Write numbers from one to ten; numbers above ten should be numerals such as 11, 12, or 13. For example, number 6 on page 48 states, "Hyphenate compound numbers from twenty-one to ninety-nine, compounds with a number as the first element, and the written form of fractions." Is it also acceptable to use 21 or 99?

I also looked for proper usage of money. Should I write \$10 or ten dollars? Which is correct? This was not included in the CMS crib sheet and is most likely in the more extensive CMS guide (17th edition). After reading this section, I know my doctoral work will succeed if I keep the CMS crib sheet handy and ensure the more extensive style guide is at hand.

6) SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

Students need examples that model what is expected, particularly on assignments. Chapter Eight EUCLID (2024, 65-68) is an integral part of the information provided for

students. It allows me to refer to examples of things to consider in my writing assignments. Even though I am nervous about turning in this first response paper because I know there will be many edits from Prof. Gulma, I am reminded again that this long doctoral journey begins with the first essay. It is not enough to read the Coursepack or the style guide. Actual examples help me to see applied rules and learn from the essay content. The sample corrections also show me what to expect when my submission is returned from Prof. Gulma.

In my daily work with restorative practices here in St. Louis, Missouri, USA, I integrate habits for human excellence into my life. This allows me to see a difficult task as an opportunity to grow in patience and persistence rather than a burden. Moreover, with these virtues, I can tackle a project with optimism and see this as a character-building experience. Correction is essential to shaping any competency, and I can become a stronger writer through this process.

7) CONCLUSION

Taking the first step in my DMCR studies at EUCLID is a relief. This first assignment was an excellent way to acclimate to the program after carefully reading the materials provided by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Prof. Kabiru Gulma. I will often refer to this packet as I progress in my studies.

When I enrolled in the International Institute for Restorative Practices (IIRP) master's program in 2015, that institution planned to have a doctoral program available in 2018. This would have allowed me to continue from my master's to a Ph.D. without interruption. However, the plan never materialized due to issues with accreditation for the extended studies. Since then, I have been searching for a purposeful direction for my educational advancement. When EUCLID was brought to my attention, it seemed a good fit. I look forward to mastering this professional writing and gaining a place in this vital field of peacebuilding.

REFERENCES

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